

NEITHER OF COTTON RAW MATERIALS ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF M ON THE QUALITY OF COTTON FIBER.

Fergana polytechnic institute qxffd(the rh)
Madaminjon Ubaidullayev Mominjonovich

Email: mubaydullaev6554@gmail.com

phone: +99(890) 274-65-54

Baxtiyorova O'g'iloyn anvarjon daughter

Email: husrasidazimova@gmail.com

phone: +998(90)776-32-50

Abstract:

In the present article an analysis of the effects of This on the quality of raw cotton cotton fiber moisture ash. Based on the result of this analysis is the lovely main experiments carried out by researchers, and recommendations are given for the use of technological processes and steam've moistening of cotton and fiber.

Key words: tempered do, cleaning, moisture, pollution, testing, steam've.

Soak the cotton fiber and cotton in the process of saving the present day republic va toe'using the following yash efficient technology to improve the quality of manufactured fibers are one of the main issues of your day. Taluqli this problem and provide analysis to give to the work of the research study is a result of wet cotton.

The study of the moisture of raw cotton to “Cotton's praise “scientific markaziAJ not get the side of the tadjik portmanteau of research work has been go. These studies of the moisture of raw cotton from 6 to 18% fall in the yield of cotton plant fiber study the effects on quality and productivity. . The results of these studies that ko'rsat demonstrates the raw cotton moisture 8.5% higher than the productivity of cotton processing enterprises decrease, the decrease of the fiber yield, fiber leads to the increase of the amount of defects and contamination. Also installed a certain konuniyat aimed at reducing the damage of the fiber [1]

depending on humidity, the lowest value of 8% at the fiber will get wet.

Saws cotton fiber cleaning machines cleaning a matter o'rga and humidity when 5,8 12,3% raw cotton, which is conducted comparative trials. Humidity 12,3%

toe‘materials raw cotton fibers from the amount of contamination present and the defects of 5,8% is significantly higher than that wet cotton is evident from the raw materials, basically trash, and we have the united ulu due to defects, this is caused by the decrease. cleaning in the effects it has. In the meantime, experience increased humidity within the framework of the processed raw cotton fiber with the length of the ko‘rsatkich that significantly improved, reducing the number of broken fibers in fiber and will identify the presence of paxmoq. In particular, increased from 34,20 32,10 mm staple length, fiber availability in paxmoq 3,20 from 4,59% and the number of broken fibers while 15,30 % from 7,90 % respectively.

The appearance of defects toe‘lish studying the causes of high humidity (11-15%) from different breeding-grade raw cotton of various cleaning in the mode of work study was conducted. Identify, broken seeds and seeds of methodology‘shma defects such as flagella appear to be one of the reasons is rising compared to the norms of the moisture of raw cotton.

Thus, 2-on-grade machines to choose from Tashkent-3 in the processing of raw cotton modal length 0.7 mm, 0.5 mm of increased staple length. Cotton wool soaked in the mixture of raw materials obtained from the mass defects in the fiber than cotton and a little namlanmagan share ko‘proq (0,3% abs.). This fact raw cotton to‘rtta, which has the effect of cleaning a pile of gear to have much higher and the three drums with being soaked up into your american cotton cleaning device of feeding can be explained. Raw cotton, cotton cleaning lead to decrease the effects of the increase of moisture.

In the process of cleaning raw cotton soaked the increase of the length of the fibers the spinning of cotton fiber to improve the technological properties and the effects are significantly ko‘rsat was. ‘Torda up to the number of defects from 348 299, 189 176 up than cotton while reduced. Koyeffsiyenti ipni quality, its relative delay and in ipni one break off their luggage cho‘zilg have increased.

8-9% moisture range of‘technological characteristics of raw cotton fiber, cotton spinning the quality and performance of ida before the processing of similar experiments on the study of the effects of the moisture a significant difference on the quality of cotton fiber is shown . “Cotton's praise “scientific center cotton plant shuralisay village toe‘citizens in the test station before the car tgsc jinlashdan raw cotton (cotton jinlash in mining) to soak maket tested the experimental device.

Ornatish that wet raw cotton 0,35-1,11% increase is provided . Moisturizing is the most effective means of parameters: $ph=82\%$, $t=54^{\circ}c$, humidity is the amount of 90 g/kg of dry air communication time – about 20-30 seconds. Soak raw cotton (selection 108 F, harvest machine, 1-varieties) from cleaning 5,31 from before .[2]

% (soak) will 6,13% to (artificial soak) mechanical shikastlanishdan protect the fiber. In the meantime, modal

The fiber obtained from cotton wool soaked in the mass of raw materials to the length of fiber compared to namlanmagan 1.3 mm, 0.8 mm staple length to o‘length, 0.5 mm high, while the central mass turned out to be far. Raw cotton fiber, and the mass of the mixture obtained in namlantirilgan namlantirilmadan at the same level share the practice of defects and toe‘become, respectively 2,70% and 2,72%, respectively.

The main raw materials of primary processing of cotton , ko‘rsatkich and continued work on the study of the effects on the quality of the product produced. Bektemir, Namangan and humidity conditions in the production of the cotton plant Romitan 7-10% range of ida, second grade, 7-13% in the range of third-grade study of the works of raw cotton.

The results of the research that ko‘rsat demonstrates defects in raw material and impurities of cotton fiber increased slightly with the increase of the amount of humidity (abs 0,14-0,22). On the other hand, the fiber length , ko‘rsatkich will improve and the short fiber content reduced. Thus, once the cleaning of raw cotton with 7,4%, 8,6% and 9,2% moisture at the level of raw cotton with o‘- check-in passengers, the length of the staple fibers of the experience (the two extreme option for) and 33.2 mm to 1,0 mm 32,2 showed that increased up to. mm, the share of short fibers 7,0% from 6,3% to decrease. Length ko‘rsatkich through spinning and improve the technological properties of fibers also improved. Taroqli harvest from cotton comb 93,44% increased from

93,82%, and comb in losses from the number 4,46% from 4,22% respectively. Luggage delay from its relative by one ipni 11,1 11.6 gf / teks increased.[3]

Soak raw cotton by foreign researchers before the cleaning processes o‘rga on to large amounts of work has been done.

Montgomery and Wooten [63] in 1958, the amount of moisture from 4,4 8,1% to toe‘present has published her research on the processing of raw cotton. The

findings ko'ra, more cotton by clean clean drying, fiber quality, yield. In the meantime, raw cotton wet , ko'comb to high-average fiber length was recorded on facts that can have a positive impact on.

Anderson 1961 year 4,1% from 6,5% in the range of humidity using raw materials from cotton to go with the research, as well as the humidity is low, which better cotton cleaning, as well as the amount of moisture to 1.5% of the cotton fibre in to save the high average length proved. about 6,5%. In the meantime, that would decrease the stability of the results of the experiment made from cotton quruqroq ipni ko'rsat was.

Humidity 3% toe'present raw cotton moisture content of 7%, which is significantly increase cleaning of raw cotton solid short fibers and ip than the weight of 2,6%led to a decrease by.[4]

In particular, high - o' - the central difference is evident 0,03 inches length (inches respectively and 1,10 1,13) was.

Kwas significantly reduced with the length of the fiber uchayishi ko'rsat was .

To explain the data obtained in 2001 and provided by Anthony Griffin was . They noted that noted, the steadfastness of a single fiber and the fiber from the seed to the surface to be attached in a wide range of power may change, but their ratio (fiber solid / be attached to the power of) is constant at 1.8. The humidity of fiber from 3% to 15% increases, a single fiber of a solid increases, but attached to the fiber strength from 3% to 11% toe'remain unchanged and the amount of moisture present in the range of 15% to slightly increases and decreases . The results of the research that ko'rsat that pre-dried raw cotton 100 ° c does not lead to drying at a temperature of the fibers appear to be damaged. Increasing drying temperature 125-175 ° C. up to the next operation in the appearance of damaged fibers toe'will lead to lish. However, 200 ° c, drying at high temperatures the number of damaged fibers fatal o'sish will lead to. 150°C and dried at low temperatures regidratlanganda cotton cotton fibers before cleaning it o'can restore the power of z. However, before cleaning, soak the raw cotton at a high temperature (200 ° c higher than) the natural properties of the fibers are dried to'liq can't restore.

Experimental studies in 2001, and anthony Griffin o'network-check-in passengers on different raw cotton-dried humidity

20 ° c to 250 ° c up to toe'is the present temperature before cleaning namlab and

later cotton. The results obtained of the quality of cotton fiber's high temperature dried ko'to rsatkich, in particular, the negative effect on fiber length and the parameters of the solid is confirmed.

Anthony in 1990, humidity 4,1%, 5,5% and 8,4% toe'present the processing of raw cotton has been suggested on the basis of the formula [75; 1089-1098-page], staple length, the same index (hv) and length distribution (Peyer) depends on the quality of fiber-like performance reflects that. The low humidity of raw cotton fiber quality data ko'rsatkich confirmed a negative impact on their health.[5]

Humidity respectively 7,4% and 3,4% toe'code from the code present in the processing of raw cotton fiber length of 35 to 37 is reduced. The moisture of raw cotton 8,4% from 4,1% in the share of short fibers with the decrease of 4,6% from 8,7%, respectively.

Based on the studies conducted by scientists and experts large amounts of Cotton toe'citizens international advisory committee (icac) in the presence of experts of the council of raw cotton cotton special methods operating on wet before cleaning on the necessity to ensure that technological recommend [80] it gave. the mass share of moisture toe'citizens 6 - 8 ,5% in the range of (the mass ratio of moisture on 6,5-9,0%). In September, 2001 published ICAC report clearly describe the effects on the quality of cotton fibre from raw cotton wet will . Noted in the report , as it was the amount of moisture 8% from the high, the fiber length was saved, but his demon-processing effects and productivity will decrease. Instead, fiber humidity of less than 5% toe'serious damage to the cotton fibers can be present, but is accompanied with a good cleaning effects.[6]

Conclusion when I finished, the information provided is known from toe'lish, according to the moisture of raw cotton fibers are of the physical-mechanical properties, the effects of local and foreign corresponds to one of the studies from the perspective of the results are available. Excessively dry & mechanical cleaning of raw cotton as a result of the escalation of decrease the length of the fibers, and fiber po'leads to the appearance of defects such as sti and broken seeds. Before the cleaning of the wet cotton of raw materials from cotton to 5-6% reduction (wet fiber increased from 4% ko'not p) and its later processing as a result of short fibers in fiber content (paxmoq) increases the amount of average fiber is formed. length of 8-10% humidity taken again o'is reduced as compared to xshab.

Raw cotton high humidity toe‘in the present case to appear in joint processing defects, mechanical damage of seeds, as well as the raw force of the roller and the car remain to be interrupted by clogged as a result will lead to a decrease in the productivity of cotton seeds.

Soak the cotton fibre in fibre will help to decrease the level of static electricity before you click click and press reduces the movement of the toy. ‘Tobreak the power of the effect of the y strip is also reduced. It should be noted that, the length of cotton fiber is one of the factors influencing on the quality of the main thread.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Гуляев Р.А., Лугачев А.Е. Разработка технологии объемного увлажнения волокна перед прессованием. Вестник молодых ученых, СанктПетербург.2004, №1 с.12-15.
2. Мардонов Б.М., Лугачев А.Е., Гуляев Р.А. Моделирование процесса увлажнения волокнистой массы в стационарном поле движущегося потока влаги: Материалы Междунар. научн. конф. «Рахматулинско-Ормонбековские чтения», - Республика Киргизстан. Бишкек. -2015. -С. 44-46.
3. Гуляев Р.А., Мардонов Б.М., Лугачев А.Е. Увлажнение волокнистой массы в вертикальной шахте встречным потоком влажного воздуха // Проблемы механики. -2015. -№3-4. -С. 56-60. (05.00.00.
4. № 6 131. Патент UZ № FAP 00390. Устройство для увлажнения волокнистого материала / Юнусов Р.Ф., Гуляев А.М., Лугачев А. Е., Гуляев Р.А., Имамутдинов М.М.// Расмий ахборотнома. – 2008, -№8.
5. Заявка на полезную модель Республики Узбекистан №FAP 20150044 «Устройство для увлажнения волокнистого материала». Авторы: Лугачев А. Е., Гуляев Р.А., Мардонов Б.М.
6. Лугачев А.А., Гуляев Р.А., Имамутдинов М.М. Разработка эффективной технологии и устройства для увлажнения хлопкового волокна перед прессованием: Материалы межвуз. научн. технич. конф. аспирантов и студентов. «Молодые ученые - развитию текстильной и легкой промышленности» (ПОИСК- 2008), -Российская Федерация. Иваново. -2008.– С.9